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Article

Trend Analysis of LIC Products for Safeguarding Future Financial Security in an AI Scenario

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ABSTRACT

The financial environment has changed as a result of artificial intelligence's (AI) rapid growth and incorporation into many facets of our lives. Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC), a major force in the insurance sector, must adjust to the changing AI landscape while maintaining policyholders' financial stability. The potential of LIC products to protect future financial security in the face of the development of AI technologies is the main subject of this study's thorough trend analysis of LIC products. The study starts by examining how artificial intelligence has revolutionised the finance industry. It demonstrates how AI-powered technologies have changed risk assessment, underwriting, claims processing, and client engagement. The study looks into how LIC is responding to an AI-driven environment. It looks at how LIC's product line has changed over time, highlighting the addition of AI-powered services like chatbot-driven customer support and risk assessment models. The analysis evaluates these innovations' possible advantages and disadvantages while taking policyholders' and the business's competitive position into account. Additionally, the study explores policyholder viewpoints regarding LIC's AI-enabled products. It measures user satisfaction, faith in AI-driven services, and data security issues using surveys and interviews. These perceptions give LIC a useful grasp of policyholder attitudes and enable it to enhance its product line through data-driven enhancements. By keeping an eye out for new developments and taking proactive steps to adjust to the AI era, LIC can maintain its position as a reliable source of financial security and protect its policyholders' futures in this quickly changing landscape.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI) Integration, Financial Landscape Transformation, LIC Product Analysis, AI-Driven Innovations, Policyholder Perspectives

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INTRODUCTION

During the era of technological advancement, the financial domain is experiencing swift and unprecedented change. As Artificial Intelligence (AI) becomes more integrated into various areas, such as banking, individuals are encouraged to reconsider their strategies for achieving long-term financial stability. Amidst the dynamic nature of the surroundings, the Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) stands out as an organisation that has demonstrated its enduring existence. LIC, renowned for its steadfast commitment to safeguarding the financial welfare of millions, has embarked on a journey of adaptation and innovation. It employs trend research to ensure that its goods align with the demands of a world driven by artificial intelligence. LIC's approach is focused on a commitment to understanding the evolving needs of its policyholders. Trend analysis allows the company to identify patterns in consumer preferences, risk perceptions, and investment choices. By employing data analytics, LIC may personalise its products to meet the preferences of a technologically savvy customer base. LIC possesses a keen understanding of the current developments in customised financial solutions and the utilisation of AI-powered chatbots for engaging with clients. They ensure that their products are in line with the expectations of the contemporary consumer.

Furthermore, in the context of artificial intelligence (AI), LIC employs trend research to enhance its offerings in response to evolving threats. LIC uses the identification of emerging risks, such as cyber threats impacting financial instruments or the effects of AI on patterns of mortality and morbidity, to develop insurance products that provide comprehensive coverage. Through this action, LIC not only safeguards the economic stability of its policyholders but also establishes itself as a proactive and forward-thinking organisation in reaction to technological disruptions.

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) with finance offers new investment opportunities and avenues for wealth creation. LIC's trend analysis involves understanding the complexities of AI-driven industries, identifying sectors poised for growth, and adapting its investment portfolio accordingly. LIC ensures its significant role in the financial ecosystem and secures the long-term financial security of its policyholders by implementing this proactive strategy, which generates profits.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is an expansive domain encompassed by the area of computer science. Artificial intelligence allows computers and machines to imitate the problem-solving and decision-making capabilities of the human brain. AI focuses on improving the functionality of operating systems to solve complex problems by utilising features such as learning, reasoning, and self-correction. Artificial intelligence (AI) is employed across several industries and sectors. Currently, it is employed in industries such as healthcare, education, banking and financial services, automotive, and gaming, among others. Artificial intelligence systems utilise intricate algorithms to facilitate rapid and efficient decision-making. The insurance industry exhibits a relatively slow rate of embracing technology innovations when compared to other sectors. The main factor responsible for this is the insurance industry's dependence on manual work. The insurance industry is integrating artificial intelligence (AI) capabilities into their day-to-day operations to improve the speed and accuracy of their performance. The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in the insurance sector would yield significant advantages and enhance operational efficiency while mitigating complexities. The insurance industry may effectively leverage artificial intelligence in multiple areas including as distribution, underwriting, pricing, claims, and product improvement. Currently, AI applications are having a significant influence on the promotion, procurement, and assessment of insurance products. The utilisation of artificial intelligence (AI) in the Indian insurance industry is broadening its

scope beyond telematics and risk evaluation. Engineering and technology start-ups in India are increasingly recognising the importance of AI applications, the growth potential, and the wide range of activities in the insurance sector. InsurTech startups in India are gradually venturing into this emerging field of application and tackling the underlying challenges in the insurance sector. According to the India Brand Equity Foundation Report (2021), there are now around 110 InsurTech start-ups operating in India.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Eling, M., Nuessle, D., and Staubli, J. (2021) examined the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on the insurance industry by applying Porter's value chain (1985) and Berliner's insurability criteria (1982). The study utilised a data set including of academic papers and industry studies. The findings revealed that artificial intelligence (AI) can enable cost savings, improve revenue recognition, and enhance risk management in the insurance industry. The study highlighted two primary benefits of AI implementation. One benefit of AI is its ability to assist insurance firms in accurately estimating the odds of loss. The second advantage is its ability to convert a few dangers from a high frequency to a low frequency. This study has prompted insurance companies to adopt a new mindset, leading them to consider creating insurance policies that are more suitable and appropriate. Seema Rawat, Aakankshu Rawat, Deepak Kumar, and A. Sai Sabitha. (2021) This study aims to investigate the determinants of claim submission in the insurance industry. The dataset underwent analysis via machine learning algorithms based on performance measures. The study demonstrated that InsurTech can enhance the ability to accurately identify and categorise clients. An examination of client demographics, patterns of claims, and analysis of claims can greatly aid in the enhancement of insurance products and the determination of appropriate rates. The policies can

be modified based on the insurance company's recognition of the profit/loss ratio and their practise of policy acceptance.

Singh and Chivukula (2020) emphasised the significance of machine learning and deep learning in resolving diverse challenges within the insurance industry. The study indicated that insurance companies encounter a variety of complex difficulties and generate diverse sets of data. The analysis determined that the implementation of AI technology in the insurance sector is currently at a rudimentary level and there is still a significant amount of progress to be made. Conventional statistical and machine learning techniques may struggle to develop accurate prediction models in the near future due to growing complexities. The study emphasised the importance of collaboration between the emerging cohort of data scientists and engineers in order to explore novel approaches for managing the distinct data of the insurance business and creating long-lasting solutions. The survey also addressed the anticipated competencies of data scientists. The report forecasted that advancements in the insurance industry, including technology like drones, the Internet of Things (IoT), and Fitbit, will pose more difficulties for AI specialists operating within the insurance sector.

The authors of the publication are Naman Kumar, Jayant Dev Srivastava, and Harshit Bisht in the year 2019. The objective of the study was to get novel insights into the operational challenges and customer discontent in the insurance industry. A limited number of global insurance businesses and InsureTechs were examined in order to construct a model that comprehends the correlation between artificial intelligence (AI) and its applications within the industry. The study discovered the extent and commercial reach of artificial intelligence in the present industry. This study demonstrated that implementing these strategies can effectively enhance

customer happiness, mitigate fraudulent activities, streamline operational processes, and ultimately boost profitability.

Riikkinen, M., Saarijärvi, H., Sarlin, P., and Lähteenmäki, I. (2018) have examined the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on enhancing value within the insurance industry. The study aimed to comprehend the function of insurance chatbots in providing customer service and generating value. The discussion briefly covered three main topics: artificial intelligence (AI), the reverse use of customer data, and service logic. The results were additionally demonstrated through case studies that examined various approaches to customer service, resulting in the production of value.

How artificial intelligence is significantly impacting the insurance industry

Through the examination of extensive data sets, which encompass past claims records, market trends, and external factors, artificial intelligence (AI) is capable of evaluating risk with enhanced precision and efficiency. This enables insurers to make informed judgments based on data when assessing policies, allowing them to set premiums with greater precision and provide customised coverage options. The outcome is a mutually beneficial scenario in which clients gain advantages from more equitable pricing, while insurers are able to manage their risks more efficiently.

The insurance sector in India has experienced a significant revolution with the introduction of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML). These state-of-the-art improvements have caused a surge of innovation, completely transforming established practises and driving the sector towards a more efficient and customer-focused future. AI and ML have greatly improved operational efficiency in the insurance industry. AI optimises operations and

liberates important human resources by automating laborious and repetitive tasks, such as data entry, document processing, and policy administration. Insurance firms can enhance their operational efficiency, minimise human errors, and allocate resources more efficiently, resulting in increased production and cost reduction.

Through the examination of extensive data sets, which encompass historical records of claims, market patterns, and external influences, artificial intelligence (AI) is capable of evaluating risk with enhanced precision and efficiency. This enables insurers to make judgments based on data, allowing them to precisely determine prices and provide customised coverage options. The outcome is a mutually beneficial scenario in which customers gain from more equitable pricing, while insurers successfully reduce their risks.

These innovations are positioned to revolutionise the sector, propelling creativity and altering conventional insurance methods.

Dipu KV, a Senior President at Bajaj Allianz GIC, highlights the various ways in which technology is currently impacting the insurance sector. Insurance firms detect probable false claims. Insurers can mitigate losses by scrutinising historical data and real-time information to effectively prevent and investigate instances of fraud.

Advanced Underwriting and Risk Assessment: Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) algorithms have the capability to analyse extensive volumes of data in order to evaluate risk with greater precision. Insurers can utilise this technology to streamline underwriting processes, resulting in faster and more effective assessments of insurance applications.

Identification and mitigation of fraudulent activities: Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms have the capability to find patterns and abnormalities within data, which can be utilised by insurance firms to accurately detect potentially fraudulent claims. Insurers can mitigate losses by scrutinising historical data and up-to-date information to effectively prevent and investigate fraudulent actions.

Customised Customer Experience: Artificial intelligence (AI)-driven chatbots and virtual assistants empower insurance companies to offer customised consumer assistance and deliver timely updates. These technologies have the capability to manage client inquiries, facilitate policy applications, and provide personalised recommendations, thereby enhancing overall customer happiness.

Claims Handling and Automating Processes: Machine learning methods for claims processing and automation can optimise and automate the workflow, minimising the need for manual involvement and enhancing overall efficiency. Insurers can accelerate the settlement process and achieve quicker claim resolution for policyholders by examining claim data and historical patterns.

Management of potential risks and determination of appropriate pricing: Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms aid insurers in precisely evaluating risks and determining policy prices accordingly. Insurers can enhance their pricing models and provide more competitive rates by examining many elements, including consumer demographics, past claims data, and external variables.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study relies on secondary data obtained from reputable sources such as media reports, news announcements, and insurance company websites. A comprehensive analysis of newspaper articles,

websites, research papers, and expert comments has been conducted to assess the current use of AI applications in LIC in India. The company is chosen based on the performance criteria.

AI AND LIFE INSURANCE CORPORATION IN INDIA

LIC has been at the forefront of Indian organisations in utilising Information Technology for policy servicing and corporate operations. The Unit Record Machines, which were introduced in the late 1950s, were gradually replaced by Microprocessor-based computers starting in 1964. In the 1980s, computers were installed in Branch and Divisional Offices to facilitate back-office activities. During the 1990s, Standard Computer Packages were created and put into use for Ordinary and Salary Savings Scheme (SSS) Policies. Over the years, we have implemented pertinent and suitable technologies to enhance our systems.

Front End Operations: LIC implemented the Front End Application Package (FEAP) to improve customer experience and services. This package allows policyholders to access various services such as receiving policy status reports, revival quotations, loan quotations, premium payments, address changes, and other on-demand services. Efficient completion of proposals and prompt dispatch of policy documents have been achieved. Our whole network of 2048 branches and 1570 satellite offices nationwide has been equipped with front-end operations and interconnected via a Wide Area Network (WAN). The Front End Package has been enhanced with new policy servicing modules that specifically address both conventional and SSS policies. These modules are designed to support various office processes, including loan processing and claims management. Each of these components contributes to the reduction of time delay and the guarantee of precision.

LIC Website: Our Internet website, which functions as a repository of information, has been improved to be dynamic and interactive. We have included an extensive compilation of information pertaining to LIC, encompassing its range of goods, office locations, and pertinent particulars. The contact information for our Zonal Offices, Zonal Training Centres, Management Development Centre, Overseas Branches, Divisional Offices, and all Branch and Satellite offices is supplied to enhance effective communication.

Online Payment Of Premium And Policy Status: (Registration is required for accessing these services) LIC offers its policyholders a distinct feature to conveniently pay premiums online without any additional fees, while also providing access to examine their policy information.

Information Centers: The operations of LIC's Centralised Call Centre began on September 29th, 2018. To access the services, simply dial the number +91-22-68276827. This number is open 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, and supports Hindi, English, as well as eight regional languages including Bengali, Gujarati, Kannada, Malayalam, Marathi, Oriya, Tamil, and Telugu. Proficient personnel are at your disposal to furnish information regarding our products, policy services, branch locations, and other pertinent organisational particulars. LIC of India currently operates 74 Customer Zones (CZEEs) across the country to offer touch point services to consumers. The CZEEs work in rotational shifts in certain regions to offer services to policy holders beyond standard working hours.

The initial stage of the deployment of LIC Mitra's artificial intelligence virtual assistant

Bengaluru-based startup CoRover has partnered with the Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) to introduce LIC Mitra, a chatbot driven by conversational AI. This collaboration aims to enhance

the digital transformation of LIC, the largest insurance firm in the country. CoRover.ai has created LIC Mitra, a software application that can be accessed through LIC's website and mobile app. The system utilises advanced technologies including Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and Natural Language Processing (NLP) to comprehend and address customer inquiries in many languages. Users can engage with LIC Mitra using voice commands thanks to the technology. LIC's digital services have been completely revolutionised by the use of our innovative technology, which drives LIC Mitra. LIC Mitra provides customers with comprehensive information on LIC products, including details about past premiums, upcoming premiums, policy maturity dates, and other relevant information. Additionally, it offers answers to general insurance-related queries. Users can obtain these facts by just inputting the insurance policy number and date of birth, while the technology handles all other tasks. We are pleased to announce that this marks the initial stage of LIC Mitra's AI virtual assistant. "Numerous additional innovations are currently being developed and will be released in the near future," stated Ankush Sabharwal, the Founder and CEO of CoRover, in his tweet. LIC Mitra improves LIC's customer support services by automating immediate responses to consumers' inquiries. Additionally, it can facilitate the increase of sales and revenue, aid in the reduction of operating expenses, optimise efficiency, and elevate client satisfaction. Furthermore, it is accessible round the clock.

LIC Mitra has the capability to handle several features, such as product information. Users can utilise LIC Mitra to acquire knowledge about different insurance products, including their characteristics and advantages. Additionally, it allows users to evaluate and contrast different insurance schemes. Current clients have the ability to verify the most up-to-current status of their policy

and access information such as the due date for premium payments and the maturity date of the policy. Customers can obtain information regarding their initial outstanding premium through LIC Mitra.

FINDINGS

Incorporation of Artificial Intelligence in the Insurance Industry

- AI enables accurate risk assessment by analysing historical data, market trends, and external factors. This enables insurers such as LIC to determine premiums with precision and provide customised coverage choices. The outcome is a mutually beneficial scenario in which clients gain advantages from more equitable pricing, while insurers effectively handle risks.
- Operational Efficiency and Innovation: The insurance sector has been transformed by the use of AI and machine learning (ML), which has automated repetitive operations such as data entry, document processing, and policy administration. This operational improvement results in reduced errors, enhanced efficiency, and decreased costs.
- AI systems facilitate expedited and more effective decision-making processes by utilising sophisticated algorithms. This encompasses a wide range of activities within the insurance industry, including the processes of distributing and evaluating insurance policies, determining appropriate pricing, handling claims, and improving insurance products.
- AI-powered solutions help insurers in detecting and mitigating fraud by finding trends that suggest possible fraudulent claims, thereby helping to avoid and investigate such occurrences. This feature

aids in reducing losses and guarantees equitable practices.

ACADEMIC AND INDUSTRY RESEARCH

- Academic research, such as Eling, Nuesse, and Staubli's study, emphasises the use of AI to provide cost savings, optimise revenue recognition, and strengthen risk management within the insurance sector. These investigations compel insurers to contemplate inventive insurance products that are in line with the changing needs of the market.
- The study conducted by Seema Rawat et al. demonstrates how InsurTech applications utilise machine learning algorithms to effectively classify consumers according to their demographics and claims patterns, therefore enhancing the product. These insights are used to adjust insurance products, improve rates, and refine policy acceptance criteria.
- Difficulties and Cooperation: Singh and Chivukula highlight the difficulties that insurers encounter when handling intricate data and stress the importance of cooperation between data scientists and engineers. Anticipated challenges arise when employing conventional statistical techniques to construct precise prediction models, owing to the increasing intricacies and technological progress.

THE TECHNOLOGICAL ADVANCEMENT OF LIC

- LIC's historical technological advancements, like as the use of Unit Record Machines in the 1950s and the current utilisation of AI-driven virtual assistants, demonstrate a

dedication to improving customer experiences and optimising operations.

- Present AI Implementations: The deployment of LIC Mitra, an AI-powered chatbot, showcases LIC's dedication to digitalization. LIC Mitra utilises advanced AI technology to provide continuous customer support, delivering extensive policy information and assisting clients with diverse inquiries.

CONCLUSION

The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in India's insurance industry, as demonstrated by LIC's innovative endeavours such as LIC Mitra, signifies a significant period of change in customer service, customised product offerings, and operational effectiveness. LIC has greatly enhanced its risk assessment, fraud detection, and customer experience by utilising advanced AI-driven solutions. These innovations not only optimise operations but also showcase LIC's dedication to utilising state-of-the-art technology for the advantage of its policyholders. AI's ongoing development is placing LIC in a leading position within the insurance market in India. By strategically adopting these breakthroughs, LIC is guaranteeing a future that is more dynamic, responsive, and focused on the needs of customers.

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